

3D Agent-Based Model of pedestrian movements for simulating COVID-19 transmission in university students

D. Alvarez Castro¹, A. Ford¹

¹ School of Engineering, Newcastle University, Newcastle upon Tyne, UK

February 15, 2021

Summary

COVID-19, a new infectious disease, constitutes a threat to humanity due to its easy transmissibility. Measures, such as the use of facemasks, lockdowns and self-isolation, have been put in place to keep the population safe, but their efficiencies should be tested. Agent-Based Modelling constitutes an interesting tool to analyse the efficiencies of these measures in society, taking into account the spatio-temporal interactions agents have during their daily routines. In this paper, the transmission of COVID-19 and restrictions applied to students living in student accommodations are simulated and tested to identify their effectiveness in controlling the spread of the pandemic.

KEYWORDS: Agent-Based Model, COVID-19, Simulations, Case-scenarios, Geo visualisation.

1. Introduction

The 30th January 2020, a public health emergency of international concern was declared (WHO, 2020a). Since then, the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has constituted a new threat to humanity. Several measures were applied to keep people safe, altering their social behaviours and movements. The success of the measures is crucial to overcome the disease, so their efficiency must be tested. Students living in student accommodations present an opportunity to study the efficiency of measures because they share living space, workplaces, and everyday routines, which constitute key factors for the transmission of the disease.

In this paper, we present a new agent-based simulation model to explore, from a spatio-temporal perspective, the transmission of COVID-19 between students living in Newcastle University accommodation. Five scenarios were simulated (No Measures, Facemasks, Lockdown, Self-isolation and Realistic) to identify their effectiveness reducing the peak values of Exposed and Infective people, the number of healthy people at the end of the outbreak, the length of the virus in the environment and the locations where disease is more transmitted.

This paper will describe the methodology adopted in the modelling (Section 2), the scenarios simulated (Section 3) and the results obtained (Section 4).

2. Methodology

Simulations of COVID-19 transmission require the combination of an Agent-Based Model (ABM) to simulate interactions between agents (students), and a mathematical epidemic model to understand how the disease is transmitted between them. In this study, students living in student accommodation were modelled as agents in an ABM framework, with interaction based on a 4-task daily routine defined for each student (**Figure 1**). These tasks included time at home, time spent at the university, shopping activities, and leisure.

Figure 1 Examples of daily routines followed by students.

The tasks were simulated with agents interacting randomly inside 3D buildings, classified in seven categories (accommodation, faculty, supermarket, leisure area, library, gym and other). Movement of students between these locations followed a pedestrian network of footpaths connecting the buildings. In addition to the students, two more interactive agents inside buildings were considered in the model: dynamic agents, representing other people that interact with students (e.g., gym clients); and static agents, representing unanimated elements that can transmit the disease through contact with an Infective agent (e.g., door handles). Finally, ‘contaminated elements’ were simulated, representing features contaminated by an Infective person through sneezing or coughing.

These agents (shapefile format) were imported into the Gama ABM platform (Taillandier et al., 2019) to simulate the spatio-temporal interactions between them (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2 Perspective view of the ABM. Students (green spheres) located inside buildings (grey polygons).

The mathematical epidemic model selected was SEIR (Li et al., 1995). This model classifies individuals in four categories depending on their status related to the disease: Susceptible, Exposed, Infective and

Recovered. Based on this classification and interactions between agents in space, the transmission of COVID-19 was simplified as follows (**Figures 3 and 4**):

- when a Susceptible individual (healthy) is within 2 metres of an Infective agent, it can be converted into Exposed based on an infection probability value (β)
- if Exposed, the individual is infected but not contagious for an incubation period (σ)
- after the incubation period, the individual becomes Infective (infectious period (γ)) and can transmit the disease to others and produce ‘contaminated elements’ in the environment
- after infectious period, the individual becomes Recovered (immune).

Figure 3 SEIR epidemiological model.

Figure 4 Flow diagram of the SEIR epidemiological model.

The interactions between the agents in the environment, combined with the SEIR epidemiological model applying COVID-19 parameters (**Table 1**), allow simulations of disease transmission.

Table 1 COVID-19 parameters applied in the simulations.

Parameter	Value	Source
β	0.0025	own calculated value based on the estimated number of secondary infections by each agent (3 as an average)
σ	5 days	(WHO, 2020b)
γ	7 days	(Public Health England, 2020)

3. Simulation Scenarios

Five scenarios for the Newcastle University case study were simulated to explore the transmission of COVID-19 between the students. In all scenarios, simulation started with two random Infective students and continued with 1-minute timesteps until the virus had run its course. **Table 2** summarises the percentage of students following them, starting days and number of total simulations per scenario.

The first scenario, ‘No Measures’, simulates an environment where no measures to reduce transmission are applied. This scenario is used as the control to test the efficiency of the other measures by comparison of results.

The ‘Facemask Use’ scenario simulates individuals wearing facemasks, which are considered to be 50% efficient (Eikenberry et. al, 2020), allowing prevention of virus transmission and self-protection.

The ‘Lockdown’ scenario simulates all agents staying at home, keeping contact only with students from the same accommodation.

The ‘Self-isolation’ scenario simulates responsible Infective individuals. Each Infective agent is asked once to self-isolate (assuming a Test and Trace contact), and they adhere to this instruction based on a probability value. If self-isolation is chosen, the individual is isolated; if the instruction is ignored individual continues with their daily routines with the ability to infect others.

The final ‘Realistic’ scenario simulates the combination of previous measures with different percentages of students following them.

Table 2 Percentage of students, starting days and number of simulations per scenario

Scenario	% of students	Starting days	Total no. of simulations
No measures	100	1	20
Facemask use	40, 60, 80, 100	1, 10, 15	48
Lockdown	40, 60, 80, 100	10, 15, 17	48
Self-isolation	40, 60, 80, 100	10, 15	32
Realistic	Combination of previous	Combination of previous	16

4. Results and analysis

The ‘No Measures’ scenario showed that disease evolves quickly in time, reaching extremely high Exposed and Infective peak values (56 and 72% of the students, respectively), being eradicated after an average of 39 days (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5 ‘No Measures’ scenario. Minimum, maximum and average values obtained after 20 simulations.

The ‘Facemask Use’ scenario showed that the use of masks helps to flatten the curves (25 and 30% reduction in Exposed and Infective peak values when all agents wear masks from Day 1) and increases the duration of the disease in time (almost double) but does not reduce the risk of infection in time (at the end of simulations only 1% of students remained susceptible).

The ‘Lockdown’ scenario showed an important reduction of Exposed and Infective peak values (29 and 40%, respectively) and a high percentage of people kept away from the disease (65%). These were achieved when the lockdown was followed by everyone and when implemented early in the outbreak (Day 10). The lifetime of the disease was reduced by four days.

The ‘Self-isolation’ scenario showed their importance in flattening the curves when at least 80% of Infective agents were self-isolated from Day 10 (29 and 35% minimum reduction in Exposed and Infective peak values, respectively). Students were only kept safe, however, when they all self-isolated when Infective (86% of students avoided infection). The lifetime of the disease was reduced by five days in the best case (100% self-isolated).

Finally, the ‘Realistic’ scenario showed a remarkable reduction in peak values (only 2 and 3% of Exposed and Infected peak values) and an impressive percentage of people kept safe from infection (95%) when facemask use, lockdown and self-isolation measures were followed by 100, 60 and 80% of agents from Days 1, 10 and 10, respectively. However, the disease stayed 83 days in the environment as an average. **Table 3** summarises the obtained results.

Table 3 Best obtained results in each of the simulated scenarios.

Scenario	First day facemask	% Mask use	First day lockdown	% lockdown	First day self-isolation	% self-isolation	Max. Exposed peak	Max Infective peak	Avg. Day	% remain susceptible
No measures	-	-	-	-	-	-	56%	72%	39	0
Facemask use	1	100	-	-	-	-	31%	42%	76	1
Lockdown	-	-	10	100	-	-	27%	32%	35	65
Self-isolation	-	-	-	-	10	80	27%	37%	75	4
Self-isolation	-	-	-	-	10	100	14%	17%	34	86
Realistic	1	100	10	60	10	80	2%	3%	83	95

Spatial analyses in all scenarios showed that the most likely locations for infection were those where many students interact for a long time (faculties and accommodation) and small buildings where many go at the same time (most popular supermarkets) (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6 Hotspot map identifying the locations where disease is more transmitted in ‘No measures’ scenario.

5. Conclusion

This paper presented the development of an ABM to simulate the spread of COVID-19 and the simulation of five case scenarios to reduce the transmission between students in a university setting. The model demonstrated that it is possible to combine spatial data and a mathematical epidemic model in ABMs to capture the dynamics of the spread of an infectious disease and to test the efficacy of control measures. The use of this type of model could help medical practitioners and university managers to plan effective responses to keep as many students as possible safe during such epidemics.

6. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank EPSRC for the funding and support given to the Centre for Doctoral Training in Geospatial Systems.

References

Eikenberry, S.E., Mancuso, M., Iboi, E., Phan, T., Eikenberry, K., Kuang, Y., Kostelich, E. and Gumel, A.B., 2020. To mask or not to mask: Modeling the potential for face mask use by the general public to curtail the COVID-19 pandemic. *Infectious Disease Modelling*.

Li, M.Y. and Muldowney, J.S., 1995. Global stability for the SEIR model in epidemiology. *Mathematical biosciences*, 125(2), pp.155-164.

Public Health England, 2020. Transmission characteristics and principles of infection prevention and control. Guidance. Updated 7 August 2020. URL <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/wuhan-novel-coronavirus-infection-prevention-and-control/transmission-characteristics-and-principles-of-infection-prevention-and-control> last visit 08/08/2020

Taillandier, P., Gaudou, B., Grignard, A., Huynh, Q.-N., Marilleau, N., P. Caillou, P., Philippon, D., & Drogoul, A. (2019). Building, composing and experimenting complex spatial models with the GAMA platform. *Geoinformatica*, (2019), 23 (2), pp. 299-322, [doi:10.1007/s10707-018-00339-6]

WHO (2020a) COVID-19 Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) Global research and innovation forum. 12 February 2020 URL [https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/covid-19-public-health-emergency-of-international-concern-\(pheic\)-global-research-and-innovation-forum](https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/covid-19-public-health-emergency-of-international-concern-(pheic)-global-research-and-innovation-forum) last visit 08/08/2020

WHO (2020b) Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): situation report, 73. World Health Organization. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/331686> last visit 09/02/2021

Biographies

David Alvarez is a PhD student in Geospatial Systems CDT, at Newcastle University. He has both experience working in industry and academia in surveying, modelling and GIS. Currently he is starting a PhD focussed on urban mobility, with the aim to help reducing congestion and pollution applying Agent-Based Modelling techniques.

Alistair Ford is a Lecturer in Geospatial Data Analytics in the Geospatial Engineering group at Newcastle University. His research interests include spatial modelling of urban environments, simulating land-use and transport systems, and their interactions with environmental factors such as extreme weather events.